

Specific botanical epithets meaning likeness

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Abstract

The topic of the present article is a linguistic analysis of specific botanical epithets meaning likeness, mainly those expressed by adjectives or participles. The types of adjectives and the different word-formation patterns are examined through which is represented similarity of the plant as a whole or its singular parts with the characteristics of another plant species or object.

The article is based on the "Conspectus of the Bulgarian vascular flora", Sofia, 2012. Besides the particular epithet, are considered the binomial names that contain it. Each Latin name is followed by its standard meaning in English or a literal translation of the Latin lexemes when the standard meaning is missing.

Keywords: Specific botanical epithets; Likeness; Types of adjectives; Word-formation

1. Introduction

The current article is part of more extensive research on linguistic structure and various connotations of binomial botanical denominations. It is based on "Conspectus of the Bulgarian vascular flora" [1]. The research considers a large group of specific botanical epithets that reflect similarities of the plant as a whole or its parts with the characteristics of another plant species or object.

International Code of Botanical Nomenclature (ICBN) [2] postulates: "The name of a species is a binary combination consisting of the name of the genus followed by a single specific epithet in the form of an adjective, a noun in the genitive, or a word in apposition (Chapter III, Section 4, Article 23.1). The present material is focused especially on the epithets expressed by adjectives, meaning likeness and similarity of the particular botanical species with other plants or objects. The specific epithets are arranged alphabetically, and their meaning is consulted in the "Etymological Dictionary of Grasses" [3], "The Names of Plants" [4], "Key to the native and foreign vascular plants in Bulgaria" [5], and "Acta plantarum" [6]. The lexemes are represented by basic forms according to the rules of Latin morphology (e. g. *falcatus*, *a*, *um* – for adjectives of the first and second declension; *aloides*, *-is* – for adjectives of the third declension with one nominative form; *amygdaliformis*, *e* – for adjectives of the third declension with two nominative forms). The binomial names that contain the particular epithet are also noted, as well as the meaning. In cases when missing a common English name of the plant, the literal translation of the Latin name is added.

According to ICBN [2], "The specific epithet, when adjectival in form and not used as a noun, agrees with the gender of the generic name" (Chapter III, Section 4, Article 23.5). Several binomial denominations demonstrate an error in the agreement, and they are marked in the research.

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2. A list of specific epithets

- **Abietinus, a, um** – resembling the genus *Abies* (fir), or growing in fir forests [4], [6].
Verbascum abietinum (synonym of *Verbascum nigrum* subsp. *Abietinum* – Dark mullein [7])
- **Abrotanifolius, a, um** – wormwood-leaved, with leaves similar to those of the *Artemisia abrotanum* (Southernwood) [4].
Senecio abrotanifolius (synonym of *Jacobaea abrotanifolia*– Pinnate-leaved ragwort [7])
- **Absinth(i)oides, -is** – wormwood-like, similar to *Artemisia absinthium* (Common wormwood) [6].
Chamaecytisus absinthioides (synonym of *Chamaecytisus eriocarpus* [7])
Erodium absinthoides (Accepted name [7]; literally: Wormwood-like storcksbill)
- **Acanthifolius, a, um** – having foliage like *Acanthus*; with thorny leaves [6].
Carlina acanthifolia (Acanthus-leaved carline-thistle)
- **Acanthoides, -is** – resembling the plants of the genus *Acanthus*, spiny [6].
Carduus acanthoides (Spiny plumeless thistle, Welled thistle)
- **Achilleifolius, a, um** – having leaves like those of the genus *Achillea* (yarrow) plants [6].
Tanacetum achilleifolium (Accepted name [7]; literally: Yarrow-leaved tansy)
- **Acinifolius, a, um** – with leaves like those of the genus *Acinos* plants, basil-thyme-leaved. [4], [6].
Veronica acinifolia (French speedwell)
- **Aegopodioides, -is** – similar to the genus *Aegopodium* (ground elder) [6].
Peucedanum aegopodioides (synonym of *Rhizomatophora aegopodioides* [7])
- **Ageratifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Ageratum* (whiteweed) plants [6].
Achillea ageratifolia (Balkan yarrow, Greek yarrow)
- **Agrimonoides, -is** – resembling the plants of the genus *Agrimonia* (agrimony) [6].
Aremonia agrimonoides (Bastard agrimony)
- **Airoides, -is** – resembling the plants of the genus *Aira* (hair-grass), with inflorescences similar to those of *Aira* [3].
Festuca airoides (Tufted fescue)
- **Aizoides, -is** – like the genus *Aizoon* (a genus of evergreen spreading plants) [6].
Saxifraga aizoides (Yellow mountain saxifrage)
- **Alliaceus, a, um** – resembling the plants of the genus *Allium* (onion): due to the appearance or smell [4], [6].
Thlaspi alliaceum (Roadside pennycress)
- **Aloides, -is** – resembling the plants of the genus *Aloë* [4], [6].
Stratiotes aloides (Water soldier)
- **Alopecuroides, -is** – resembling the genus *Alopecurus* (foxtail grass) plants, usually in respect of the inflorescences [3].
Crypsis alopecuroides (Foxtail prickle-grass)
- **Alsiniifolius, a, um** – with ovate hairy leaves like the genus *Alsine* (chickweed, stitchwort) [3].
Epilobium alsinifolium (Chickweed willowherb)
- **Althaeoides, -is** – like the genus *Althaea* (marshmallow), usually due to the appearance of the leaves [6].
Convolvulus althaeoides (Mallow bindweed, Mallow-leaved bindweed)
- **Alyssoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Alyssum* (madwort) plants [6].
Alyssum alyssoides (Pale madwort)
- **Ambrosioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Ambrosia* (ragweed) plants [6].
Chenopodium ambrosioides (synonym of *Dysphania ambrosioides* [7] – Wormseed, Mexican tea)
- **Amygdaliformis, e** – almond-like (*Amygdala* – almond) [6].
Pyrus amygdaliformis (Almond-leaved pear)
- **Amygdaloides, -is** – almond-like (*Amygdala* – almond) [6].
Euphorbia amygdaloides (Wood spurge)
- **Anagallidifolius, a, um** – with leaves like the genus *Anagallis* (pimpernel) plants [6].
Epilobium anagallidifolium (Pimpernel willowherb, Alpine willowherb)
- **Androsaceus, a, um** – similar to the genus *Androsace* (rock jasmine) plants [6].
Saxifraga androsacea (Scree saxifrage)
- **Anisiacus, a, um** – anisic, relating to *Anisum* (anise) [6].
Alchemilla anisiaca (Accepted name [7]; literally: Anisic lady's mantle)
- **Annulatus, a, um** – ring-like, having ring-shaped organs (*annulus* – ring) [4], [6].
Hypericum annulatum (Accepted name [7]; literally: Ring-like St. John's wort)
- **Anserinus, a, um** – pertaining to geese (*anser* – goose), [4], [6].

Potentilla anserina (synonym of *Argentina anserina* [7]; Silverweed cinquefoil: the specific epithet refers to the leaves in the shape of a goose foot [6])

- **Anthericoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Anthericum* (asphodel) plants [4].
Asyneuma anthericoides (Accepted name [7])
- **Apifer, era, erum** – bee-like, literally: bearing bees (*apis* – bee) [4].
Ophrys apifera (Bee orchid: the specific epithet is because of the flower similar to a bee [6])
- **Aquilegifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Aquilegia* (columbine) plants [6]
Thalictrum aquilegifolium (Siberian columbine meadow-rue)
- **Arenariiformis, e** – having the shape of the genus *Arenaria* (sandwort) plants.
Stachys arenariiformis (Accepted name [7])
- **Arifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Arum* plants [6].
Rumex arifolius (Maiden sorrel)
- **Armoracioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Armoracia* (horseradish) plants [6].
Rorippa x armoracioides (Walthamstow yellowcress)
- **Artemisiifolius, a, um** – with leaves like the genus *Artemisia* (mugwort, wormwood) plants [6].
Ambrosia artemisifolia (Common ragweed)
- **Arundinaceus, a, um** – reed-like (*Arundo* – reed) [4], [6].
Alopecurus arundinaceus (Creeping meadow foxtail, Creeping foxtail)
Calamagrostis arundinacea (Korean feather reed grass)
Festuca arundinacea (Tall fescue)
Glyceria arundinacea (Accepted name [7]; literally: Reed-like sweet-grass)
Molinia arundinacea (Accepted name [7], synonym of *Molinia caerulea* – Purple moor-grass)
Phalaris arundinacea (Ribbon grass)
- **Asparagifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Asparagus* (sparrow-grass) plants [6].
Galium asparagifolium (Accepted name [7])
- **Asperuloides, -is** – resembling the plants in the genus *Asperula* (woodruff).
Bupleurum asperuloides (Accepted name [7])
- **Asphodeloides, -is** – resembling the genus *Asphodelus* (asphodel) plants [6].
Geranium asphodeloides (Accepted name [7]; literally: Asphodel crane's-bill)
- **Asplenifolius, a, um** – having foliage like genus *Asplenium* (spleenwort) plants [6].
Achillea asplenifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Spleenwort-leaved yarrow)
- **Asteroanthus, a, um** – with star-like flowers (*astrum* – star).
Alchemilla asteroantha (Accepted name [7]; literally: Star-flowered lady's mantle)
- **Athamanticus, a, um** – resembling the genus *Athamanta* (a flowering plant in the *Apiaceae* family) plants [6].
Meum athamanticum (Baldmoney)
- **Auritus, a, um** – having ear-shaped parts or appendages, eared (*auris* – ear) [4].
Salix aurita (Eared willow – having vegetative organs resembling long ears [6])
- **Baccatus, a, um** – having berries; similar to a berry, or having parts or
Organs similar to a berry (*bacca* – berry) [6].
Taxus baccata (Golden irish yew)
- **Bellidifolius, a, um** – having foliage like the genus *Bellis* (daisy) plants [6].
Saponaria bellidifolia (Daisy-leaved soapwort)
Thlaspi bellidifolium (synonym of *Noccaea bellidifolia* [7])
- **Bellidioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Bellis* (daisy) plants [6], daisy-like.
Veronica bellidioides (Daisy-leaved speedwell)
- **Betonifolius, a, um** – having foliage like the genus *Betonica* (betony) plants [4]. [6].
Convolvulus betonicifolius (Shaggy bindweed)
- **Betulus, a, um** – epithet coined by Linnaeus for a supposed resemblance to the birch, birch-like (*Betula* – birch) [6].
Carpinus betulus (European hornbeam)

Note: There is a probable mistake in the agreement – the specific epithet should be *betula* because the generic name *Carpinus* is feminine gender.

- **Blitoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Blitum* (a genus of flowering plants in the amaranth family) plants [6].
Amaranthus blitoides (Prostrate pigweed)
- **Botryoides, -is** – like a bunch of grapes, a reference to the racemose inflorescences (*botrys* – cluster, bunch) [6].

- Muscari botryoides* (Compact grape hyacinth)
- **Bromoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Bromus* (brome grass) plants [6].
Achnatherum bromoides (Accepted name [7])
Vulpia bromoides (synonym of *Festuca bromoides* [7] – Squirrel-tail fescue, Barren fescue, Brome fescue)
- **Bryoides, -is** – similar to moss, moss-like (*bryon* – moss) [4], [6].
Saxifraga bryoides (Mossy saxifrage)
- **Bugulifolius, a, um** – having bugle-like leaves.
Verbascum bugulifolium (Accepted name [7]; literally: Bugle-leaved mullein)
- **Bupleuroides, -is** – resembling the genus *Bupleurum* (ox-rib) plants [4], [6].
Silene bupleuroides (Accepted name [7])
- **Cannabinus, a, um** – hemp-like (*Cannabis* – hemp) [4], [6].
Althaea cannabina (Hemp-leaved hollyhock – due to the leaves' shape [6])
Eupatorium cannabinum (Hemp-agrimony)
- **Capitatus, a, um** – resembling a head, with inflorescence or stigma condensed to a sphere-like structure (*caput* – head) [4], [6].
Asperula capitata (synonym of *Hexaphylla capitata* [7]; literally: Headed woodruff)
Dianthus capitatus (literally: Headed pink)
Echinaria capitata (Accepted name [7])
Juncus capitatus (Dwarf rush)
Linum capitatum (Yellow Balkan flax)
Ziziphora capitata (Accepted name [7])
- **Carinatus, a, um** – keeled, with a protruding part shaped like a keel (*carina* – keel) [4], [6].
Allium carinatum (Keeled garlic)
Valerianella carinata (Keel-fruited cornsalad)
- **Carpinifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Carpinus* (hornbeam) plants [6].
Ostrya carpinifolia (Hop hornbeam)
- **Carvifolius, a, um** – having foliage like Caraway (*Carum carvi* – caraway) [6].
Peucedanum carvifolium (synonym of *Dichopetalum carvifolia* [7])
Selinum carvifolia (Cambridge milk parsley)

Note: There is a probable mistake in the agreement – the specific epithet should be *carvifolium* because the generic name *Selinum* is neuter gender.

- **Caryophyllaceus, a, um** – pinkish, clove-like, which resembles carnation in appearance or fragrance (*caryophyllon* – clove) [4], [6].
Orobanche caryophyllacea (Clove-scented broomrape)
Rosa caryophyllacea (Accepted name [7]; literally: Clove-like rose)
- **Caryophylleus, a, um** – with hard leaves (*caryon* – walnut) [6].
Aira caryophyllea (Silver hairgrass)
Carex caryophyllea (Vernal sedge)
- **Catenatus, a, um** – linked in a chain, similar to a chain (*catena* – chain) [4], [6].
Veronica catenata (Pink water speedwell)
- **Cerasifer, era, erum** – having fruits in the shape of cherry, literally: bearing cherries (*cerasum* – cherry) [4], [6].
Prunus cerasifera (Cherry plum)
- **Cerasifolius, a, um** – having cherry-like leaves (*cerasus* – cherry) [6].
Rubus cerasifolius (synonym of *Rubus geniculatus* [7]; literally: Cherry-leaved blackberry)
- **Cerastoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Cerastium* (mouse-eared chickweed) plants [6].
Cerastium cerastoides (Mountain chickweed, Starwort mouse-ear)
Hypericum cerastoides (Alpine Saint John's wort)
- **Chamaedryfolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Chamaedrys* (an old name used by Theophrastus for germander, dwarf oak) plants [6].
Spiraea chamaedryfolia (Germander meadowsweet meadowsweet, Elm-leaved spirea)
- **Chamaemelifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Chamaemelum* (chamomile) plants [6].
Artemisia chamaemelifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Chamomile-leaved wormwood)
- **Cheiranthoides, -is** – resembling the plants in the genus *Cheiranthus* (wallflower) [4], [6].
Erysimum cheiranthoides (Treacle-mustard, Wormseed wallflower)
- **Chenopodioides, -is** – resembling the plants in the genus *Chenopodium* (goosefoot) [6].

- Chenopodium chenopodioides* (synonym of *Oxybasis chenopodioides* [7] – Low goosefoot)
- **Cichoraceus, a, um** – similar to the genus *Cichorium* (chicory) plants [6].
Leontodon cichoraceus (synonym of *Scorzoneroides cichoriacea* [7]; literally: Chicory hawkbit)
 - **Ciconius, a, um** – relating to *Ciconia* (stork whose long beak recalls the shape of the fruit) [6].
Erodium ciconium (Common stork's bill)
 - **Cicutarius, a, um** – resembling the plants in the genus *Cicuta* (water hemlock): due to the leaves' shape [4], [6].
Erodium cicutarium (Common stork's bill, Redstem filaree)
 - **Clavatus, a, um** – club-shaped, having organs similar to a club (*clava* – club, paddle) [4], [6].
Lycopodium clavatum (Common club moss)
 - **Clypeatus, a, um** – shield-shaped, with a shield (*clypeus* – round shield): due to the shape of the pods [6].
Fibigia clypeata (Roman shields)
 - **Clypeolatus, a, um** – shaped like a little shield (*clypeolus* – small shield).
Achillea clypeolata (Accepted name [7]; Balkan yarrow)
 - **Cochlearifolius, a, um** – having spoon-shaped leaves (*cochlear* – spoon) [6].
Campanula cochlearifolia (Earleaf bellflower, Fairy's-thimble)
 - **Colchiciflorus, a, um** – having flowers like the genus *Colchicum* (autumn crocus) plants [6].
Sternbergia colchiciflora (Slender sternbergia)
 - **Columbarius, a, um** – dove-colored, dove-like (*Columba* – dove) [4], [6].
Scabiosa columbaria (Small scabious, Dove pincushion)
 - **Columbinus, a, um** – relating to the dove, liked by pigeons, dove-like (*Columba* – dove) [4], [6].
Geranium columbinum (Long-stalked crane's-bill)
 - **Conyzifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Conyza* (horseweed) plants [6].
Crepis conyzifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Horseweed-leaved hawksbeard)
 - **Conopseus, a, um** – looking like a mosquito, gnat-like (*κόνωψ* – gnat) [4].
Gymnadenia conopsea (Fragrant orchid: the specific epithet refers to the long spur similar to the mouthparts of mosquitoes [6])
 - **Cordatus, a, um** – heart-shaped (*cor* – heart): usually reference to the leaf shape [4], [6].
Listera cordata (synonym of *Neottia cordata* [7] – Lesser twayblade, Heartleaf twayblade)
Tilia cordata (Small-leaved lime)
Vicia cordata (synonym of *Vicia sativa* subsp. *Cordata* [7]; literally: Heart-leaved vetch)
 - **Cordifolius, a, um** – having heart-shaped leaves (*cor* – heart) [4], [6].
Globularia cordifolia (Heart-leaved globe daisy)
 - **Cordiger, era, erum** – heart-bearing (*cor* – heart, and *fero* – carry): for the shape of the leaves or other organs [6].
Dactylorhiza cordigera (Heart-shaped lip dactylorhiza)
 - **Coronopifolius, a, um** – with leaves like the genus *Coronopus* (swinecress) plants.
Teesdalia coronopifolia (Lesser shepherdscrews)
 - **Corymbosoides, -is** – similar to corymb (inflorescence type in the form of a flat-topped flower cluster [4]).
Alyssum corymbosoides (synonym of *Odontarrhena corymbosoidea* [7])
 - **Crithmifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Crithmum* (samphire, sea fennel) plants [6].
Achillea crithmifolia (Crithmium-leaved yarrow)
 - **Crocifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Crocus* (saffron) plants [6].
Tragopogon crocifolius (Accepted name [7]; literally: Saffron-leaved goat's-beard)
 - **Cuminoides, -is** – resembling the plants in the genus *Cuminum* (cumin) [6].
Lagoecia cuminoides (Common wild cumin)
 - **Cuneifolius, a, um** – with wedge-shaped leaves broader to the apex (*cuneus* – wedge) [4], [6].
Asplenium cuneifolium (Serpentine spleenwort)
Centaurea cuneifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Wedge-leaved knapweed)
Satureja cuneifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Wedge-leaved savory)
 - **Cymbalarius, a, um** – relating to the genus *Cymbalaria*, cymbal-like (*cymbalum* – a flat round percussion instrument) [6].
Veronica cymbalaria (Glandular speedwell)
 - **Cynapioides, -is** – resembling *Cynapium* (dog-parsley) [6].
Huetia cynapioides (synonym of *Geocaryum cynapioides* [7])
 - **Daucoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Daucus* (carrot) plants, usually for the leaves [6].
Orlaya daucoides (Flat-fruited orlaya)
Stefanoffia daucoides (Accepted name [7])
 - **Delphinanthus, a, um** – having flowers like the genus *Delphinium* (larkspur) plants [6].

- Viola delphinantha* (Accepted name [7]; literally: Larkspur-flowered violet)
- **Deltoides, -is** – delta-shaped, triangular-shaped (Δ – the fourth letter of the Greek alphabet) [4], [6].
Dianthus deltoides (Maiden pink)
Juniperus deltoides (Eastern prickly juniper)
 - **Disciformis, e** – disk-shaped (*discus* – disk) [6].
Medicago disciformis (Veinless medick)
 - **Discoideus, a, um** – disk-like, disk-shaped (*discus* – disk) [4], [6].
Matricaria discoidea (Wild chamomile, Disc mayweed, Rayless chamomile)
Valerianella discoidea (synonym of *Valeriana discoidea* [7]; literally: Disk-like corn-salad)
 - **Echioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Echium* (viper's bugloss) plants [4], [6].
Hieracium echioides (synonym of *Pilosella echioides* [7])
Onosma echioides (Hairy golden-drup)
Picris echioides (synonym of *Helminthotheca echioides* [7] – Prickly oxtongue)
 - **Elaeagnifolius, a, um** – having foliage like the genus *Elaeagnus* (silverberry, oleaster) plants [6].
Pyrus elaeagnifolia (synonym of *Pyrus elaeagrifolia* [5] – Oleaster-leaved pear)
 - **Ensifolius, a, um** – having sword-shaped leaves (*ensis* – sword) [6].
Inula ensifolia (Swordleaf inula)
 - **Epipactoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Epipactis* (helleborine) plants [6].
Cephalanthera epipactoides (Eastern hooded helleborine)
 - **Erucifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Eruca* (rocket) plants.
Quercus erucifolia (synonym of *Quercus robur* subsp. *Pedunculiflora* [7] – Pedunculate oak)
Senecio erucifolius (synonym of *Jacobaea erucifolia* [7] – Hoary ragwort)
 - **Eruciformis, e** – looking like *Eruca* (rocket) [6].
Beckmannia eruciformis (European slough-grass)
Brachiaria eruciformis (synonym of *Moorochloa eruciformis* [7] – Sweet signal grass)
 - **Ervoides, e** – resembling the genus *Ervum* (vetch) plants [6].
Lens ervoides (synonym of *Vicia lenticula* [7])
 - **Fabarioides, e** – resembling *faba* (bean), bean-like {4}, [6].
Silene fabarioides (Accepted name [7]; literally: Bean-like catchfly)
 - **Falcatus, a, um** – sickle-shaped (*falx* – sickle): due to the shape of some organs, e.g. Leaves or fruits [6].
Bupleurum falcatum (Sickle-leaved hare's-ear)
Ceratocephalus falcatum (synonym of *Ranunculus falcatum* [5])
Euphorbia falcata (Sickle spurge)
Medicago falcata (Sickle medick, Sickle alfalfa)
 - **Farfarus, a, um** – relating to *farfarus* (plant cited by Plautus and Pliny); another possible interpretation is a reference to the Farfa River that flows into the Tiber [6].
Tussilago farfara (Coltsfoot)
 - **Ferulaceus, a, um** – resembling the genus *Ferula* (giant fennel) plants, fennel-like {4}, [6].
Bunium ferulaceum (Balkan pignut)
Prangos ferulacea (Accepted name [7])
 - **Festuciformis, e** – resembling the genus *Festuca* (fescue) plants [6].
Puccinellia festuciformis (Accepted name [7]; literally: Fescue-shaped alkali grass)
 - **Ficifolius, a, um** – fig-leaved (*Ficus* – fig) [6].
Chenopodium ficifolium (Fig-leaved goosefoot)
 - **Filiculoides, -is** – similar to a small fern (*filicula* – small fern) [4], [6].
Azolla filiculoides (Water fern)
 - **Filiformis, e** – thread-like, slender (*filum* – thread) [4], [6].
Juncus filiformis (Thread rush)
Lathyrus filiformis (Accepted name [7]; literally: Threadlike vetchling)
Veronica filiformis (Slender speedwell, Thread-stalk speedwell)
 - **Flabellatus, a, um** – fan-shaped, fan-like (*flabellum* – fan) [4], [6].
Alchemilla flabellata (Fan lady's mantle)
 - **Florentinoides, -is** – obscure etymology, probably: Florentine-like (from *florentinus* – Florentine and *-oides* – similar)
Hieracium florentinoides (synonym of *Pilosella florentinoides* [5])
 - **Foeniculaceus, a, um** – resembling the genus *Foeniculum* (fennel) plants due to the leaves' shape or the scent [6].
Turgeniopsis foeniculacea (Accepted name [7])

- **Fragariiflorus, a, um** – having flowers like the genus *Fragaria* (strawberry) plants.
Rubus fragariiflorus (this is a taxonomically valueless local or singular biotype [7])
- **Galericulatus, a, um** – similar to a small cap, helmet-shaped (*galericulum* – hat but also a small helmet or wig) [6].
Scutellaria galericulata (Common skullcap, Marsh skullcap, Hooded skullcap: due to the corolla shape that seems to be covered by a small hat [6])
- **Geniculatus, a, um** – knee-shaped, bent at an angle like a knee (*geniculum* – diminutive from *genu* knee): for plants with bent culms or awns [3], [6].
Aegilops geniculata (Ovate goatgrass)
Alopecurus geniculatus (Water foxtail, Marsh foxtail)
Rubus geniculatus (False Himalayan berry)
- **Genistifolius, a, um** – having foliage like the genus *Genista* (broom) plants [6].
Linaria genistifolia (Broomleaf toadflax)
- **Genistoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Genista* (broom) plants, broom-like [4], [6].
Lotononis genistoides (Accepted name [7]; literally: Broom-like lotononis)
- **Gentianoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Gentiana* (gentian) plants [6].
Plantago gentianoides (Accepted name [7]; literally: Gentian-like plantain)
- **Geoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Geum* (avens) plants [4].
Waldsteinia geoides (Accepted name [7])
- **giganteiformis, e** – similar to a giant, very large [4].
Dianthus giganteiformis (Accepted name [7]; literally: Giant-like carnation)
- **Gladius, a, um** – sword-like, having acuminate parts like a sword (*gladius* – sword) [4], [6].
Astragalus gladius (Accepted name [7]; literally: Sword-like milkvetch)
Trigonella gladiata (Accepted name [7]; literally: Sword-like fenugreek)
- **Graecizans, -antis** – imitating or reminding some Greek plants [6]; becoming widespread [4].
Amaranthus graecizans (Mediterranean amaranth, Short-tepalled pigweed)
- **Gramineus, a, um** – grass-like, with thin leaves similar to grasses, or living on the grass (*gramen* – grass) [4], [6].
Alisma gramineum (Narrowleaf water-plantain, Ribbon-leaf water-plantain)
Iris graminea (Grass-leaved flag, Grass-leaved iris)
Najas graminea (Ricefield water-nymph)
Potamogeton gramineus (Various-leaved pondweed, Grass-leaved pondweed, Grassy pondweed)
Stellaria graminea (Grass-leaved starwort, Lesser starwort, Grass-like starwort)
- **Graminifolius, a, um** – having grass-like leaves (*gramen* – grass) [6].
Edraianthus graminifolius (Blue grassy bells)
Lepidium graminifolium (Grass-leaved pepperwort)
- **Gypsophiloides, -is** – resembling the genus *Gypsophila* (baby's-breath) plants [6].
Arenaria gypsophiloides (synonym of *Eremogone gypsophiloides* [7]; literally: Baby's-breath sandwort)
- **Halimifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *Atriplex halimus* (Mediterranean saltbush) [6].
Hieracium halimifolium (synonym of *Hieracium brevifolium* subsp. *halimifolium* [7])
- **Hamosius** – derivative from *hamosus*: recurved as a hook, having hook-shaped organs (*hamus* – hook) [6]. Probably a comparative form for neuter.
Taraxacum hamosius (Accepted name [7])
- **Hamosus, a, um** – hook-like, strongly recurved, with hook-shaped organs (*hamus* – hook) [6].
Astragalus hamosus (European milkvetch: reference to the shape of the legume [6])
- **Hamulosus, a, um** – similar to a small hook, due to the presence of folded, curved organs (*hamulus* – small hook) [4], [6].
Carduus hamulosus (Accepted name [7]; literally: Small- hooked plumeless-thistle)
Dichostylis hamulosa (synonym of *Cyperus hamulosus* [7])
- **Hastatus, a, um** – spear-shaped, formed like an arrow-head (*hasta* – spear) [4], [6].
Atriplex hastata (synonym of *Atriplex prostrata* [5] – Spear-leaved orache, Hastate orache)
Salix hastata (Halberd-leaved willow)
- **Hastifolius, a, um** – having spear-shaped leaves (*hasta* – spear) [6].
Scutellaria hastifolia (Spear-leaved skullcap)
- **Hederaceus, a, um** – pertaining to ivy, similar to ivy: usually refers to the shape of the leaves or the climbing habit (*Hedera* – ivy) [6].
Glechoma hederacea (Ground-ivy, Gill-over-the-ground)
- **Hederifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Hedera* (ivy) plants [6].

Cyclamen hederifolium (Ivy-leaved cyclamen)

Veronica hederifolia (Ivy-leaved speedwell)

- **Hieracioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Hieracium* (hawkweed) plants, hawkweed-like [4], [6].
Picris hieracioides (Hawkweed oxtongue)
- **Hirundinarius, a, um** – swallow-like (*hirundo* – swallow) [4], [6].
Vincetoxicum hirundinaria (White swallow-wort: reference to the swallow-tail-shaped root)

Note: There is a probable mistake in the agreement – the specific epithet should be *hirundinarium* because the genus name *Vincetoxicum* is neuter gender.

- **Holciformis, e** – similar to the genus *Holcus* (velvetgrass) plants [6].
Piptatherum holciforme (Hairy ricegrass, Hairy millet grass)
- **Hordeistichos, -on** – having spikes similar to those of *Hordeum* (barley) [6].
Carex hordeistichos (Barley sedge)
- **Hypericifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Hypericum* (St. John's wort) plants [6].
Spiraea hypericifolia (Iberian meadowsweet)
- **Hyssopifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Hyssopus* (Hyssop) plants [6].
Hypericum hyssopifolium (Hyssop-leaved St. John's wort)
Lythrum hyssopifolia (Hyssop loosestrife, Grass-poly)

Note: There is a probable mistake in the agreement – the specific epithet should be *hyssopifolium* because the genus name *Lythrum* is neuter gender.

- **Insectifer, era, erum** – literally: bearing insects (*insectum* – insect) [4], [6].
Ophrys insectifera (Fly orchid: reference to the flower shape resembling an insect [6])
- **Junceus, a, um** – rush-like, resembling *Juncus* (*Juncus* – rush) [4], [6].
Brassica juncea (Brown mustard)
Chondrilla juncea (Rush skeleton-weed, Naked weed)
Spartium junceum (Spanish broom)
- **Lamiifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Lamium* (dead-nettle) plants [4].
Teucrium lamiifolium (Accepted name [7]; literally: Dead-nettle-leaved germander)
- **Lanceolatus, a, um** – lance-shaped (*lanceola* – short spear), narrowed and tapered at both ends [4].
Alisma lanceolatum (Lanceleaf water plantain, Narrow-leaved water plantain)
Bromus lanceolatus (Mediterranean brome)
Epilobium lanceolatum (Spear-leaved willowherb)
Plantago lanceolata (Ribwort plantain, Narrowleaf plantain)
- **Lapathifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *lapathum* (sorrel or dock) [6].
Persicaria lapathifolia (Pale persicaria, Pale smartweed,)
- **Lappaceus, a, um** – burdock-like (*lappa* – bur, burdock) [4].
Trifolium lappaceum (Burdock clover)
- **Lathyroides, -is** – resembling the genus *Lathyrus* (vetchling) plants [6].
Vicia lathyroides (Spring vetch)
- **Laureolus, a, um** – looking like a small laurel (*Laurus* – laurel) [6].
Daphne laureola (Spurge laurel)
- **Laurinus, a, um** – laurel-like (*Laurus* – laurel) [4], [6].
Hieracium laurinum (synonym of *Hieracium vasconicum* subsp. *laureolum* [7])
- **Leporinus, a, um** – hare-like: which resembles or is preferred by hares (*lepus* – hare) [6].
Hordeum leporinum (synonym of *Hordeum murinum* subsp. *leporinum* [7]; literally: Hare barley)
- **Ligularis, e** – strap-like (*ligula* – small tongue) [4].
Cirsium ligulare (synonym of *Lophiolepis ligularis* [7])
- **Limonifolius, a, um** – having leaves like those of lemon [6].
Asyneuma limonifolium (Accepted name [7])
- **Linarioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Linaria* (toadflax) plants [4].
Hypericum linarioides (Accepted name [7])
- **Linifolius, a, um** – having flax-like leaves (*Linum* – flax) [6].
Lathyrus linifolius (Bitter vetch, Heath pea)
- **Linoides, -is** – flax-like, usually with reference to the leaves (*Linum* – flax) [4], [6].
Radiola linoides (Allseed flax)
- **Linophyllos, -on (linophyllus, a, um)** – having leaves like the genus *Linum* (flax) plants [6].

- Thesium linophyllum* (Accepted name [7])
- **Loliaceus, a, um** – resembling the genus *Lolium* (ryegrass) plants, especially regarding the inflorescence [3].
Festulolium loliaceum (synonym of *Lolium x elongatum* [7])
Lolium loliaceum (synonym of *Lolium rigidum* [7] – Rigid ryegrass)
 - **Lonchitis, e** – spear-shaped, lance-shaped (*lonche* – spear) [4].
Polystichum lonchitis (Northern holly fern: due to the edges of the leaves, similar to spearheads [6]).
 - **Lotoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Lotus* plants, trefoil-like [4].
Glinus lotoides (Lotus sweetjuice, Damascisa)
 - **Lunarius, a, um** – similar to the moon due to the presence of organs shaped like a crescent (*luna* – moon) [6].
Alchemilla lunaria (Accepted name [7]; literally: Moon-shaped lady's mantle)
 - **Lupuliformis, e** – hop-shaped (*Humulus lupulus* – Common hop; *lupulus* – wolf cub) [4].
Cuscuta lupuliformis (Hop dodder, Willow dodder)
 - **Lupulinus, a, um** – resembling hop (*Humulus lupulus* Common hop; *lupulus* wolf cub) [4].
Medicago lupulina (Black medick, Hop clover)
 - **Luzulinus, a, um** – relating to the genus *Luzula* (wood rush), *Luzula*-like [4], [6].
Luzula luzulina (Accepted name [7])
 - **Luzuloides, -is** – resembling the genus *Luzula* (wood rush) plants [6].
Luzula luzuloides (White wood-rush, Oak-forest wood-rush)
 - **Margaritaceus, a, um** – resembling a pearl, pearly (*margarita* – pearl) [4], [6].
Allium margaritaceum (synonym of *Allium sardoum* [7]; literally: Pearl-like onion)
 - **Marmoreus, a, um** – marbled, marble-like, with veins of color: reference to the sheaths of the new culms (*marmor* – marble) [6].
Hieracium marmoreum (Accepted name [7]; literally: Marbled hawkweed)
Sempervivum marmoreum (Accepted name [7]; literally: Marbled houseleek)
 - **Matricariifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Matricaria* (chamomile) plants [6].
Botrychium matricariifolium (Chamomile grape-fern, Daisy-leaf grape-fern, Matricary grape-fern)
 - **Meleagroides, -is** – similar to *Meleagris* (Guinea fowl): probably due to the spotted coloration that recalls the exterior of this bird [6].
Fritillaria meleagroides (Accepted name [7])
 - **Militaris, e** – pertaining to soldiers, like a soldier, upright (*miles* – soldier) [4].
Orchis militaris (Military orchid: for the shape of the flower that recalls a human figure with a helmet on his head [6])
 - **Myosuroides, -is** – resembling a mouse tail (*μῦς* – mouse, and *οὐρά* – tail), due to the appearance of the inflorescence [6].
Alopecurus myosuroides (Slender meadow foxtail, Black-grass)
Kobresia myosuroides (synonym of *Carex myosuroides* [7] – Bellardi bog sedge)
 - **Myrsinites, -is** – resembling *Myrsine* (an ancient name for the myrtle in Dioscorides), myrtle-like [6].
Euphorbia myrsinites (Myrtle spurge, Blue spurge, Broad-leaved glaucous-spurge)
 - **Myrtifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Myrtus* (myrtle) plants, myrtle-leaved [4].
Rhododendron myrtifolium (synonym of *Rhododendron kotschyi* [7]; literally: Myrtle-leaf rhododendron)
 - **Napulifer, era, erum** – literally: bearing turnip, turnip-shaped (*napulus* – small turnip).
Centaurea napulifera (Accepted name [7]; literally: Turnip-shaped knapweed)
 - **Narcissiflorus, a, um** – having flowers like the genus *Narcissus* (daffodil) plants [6].
Anemone narcissiflora (synonym of *Anemonastrum narcissiflorum* [7] – Narcissus-flowered anemone, Narcissus anemone)
 - **Nardiformis, e** – spikenard-shaped (*Nardus* – spikenard) [4].
Dianthus nardiformis (Dobrogea carnation)
 - **Nummularius, a, um** – coin-shaped, rounded (*nummulus* – coin): probably for the golden color of the corollas, similar to a golden coin [6].
Helianthemum nummularium (Common rock-rose)
Lysimachia nummularia (Creepin jenny, Moneywort)
 - **Oleifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *Olea* (olive), olive-leaved [6].
Aster oleifolius (synonym of *Galatella villosa* [7]; literally: Olive-leaved aster)
 - **Oleoides, -is** – olive-like (*Olea* – olive) [6].
Daphne oleoides (Olive daphne)
 - **Onobrychioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Onobrychis* (sainfoin) plants [6].
Vicia onobrychioides (Sainfoin vetch)

- **Ophioglossifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Ophioglossum* (adder's-tongue fern) plants, snake's-tongue-leaved [4], [6].
Ranunculus ophioglossifolius (Adder's-tongue spearwort)
- **Opulifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *opulus* (an obsolete name for the guelder rose [4]).
Chenopodium opulifolium (Grey goosefoot)
- **Orchideus, a, um** – similar to the genus *Orchis* (orchid) plants [6].
Veronica orchidea ("Blue fingers" speedwell)
- **Ornithopodioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Ornithopus* (bird's-foot) plants, bird-footed [4].
Cleome ornithopodioides (Bird spiderflower)
- **Oryzoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Oryza* (rice) [6].
Echinochloa oryzoides (Early barnyard grass)
Leersia oryzoides (Rice cutgrass)
- **Oviniformis, e** – resembling a sheep (*Ovis* – sheep).
Festuca oviniformis (Accepted name [7])
- **Palmatus, a, um** – shaped like the hand palm, with five or more veins arising from one point (*palma* – palm): reference to the appearance of the leaves [4].
Eryngium palmatum (Accepted name [7]; literally: Palm-shaped eryngo)
- **Paniceus, a, um** – similar to millet-grain (*Panicum* – millet) [4], [6].
Carex panicea (Carnation sedge)
- **Paniculatus, a, um** – having inflorescences similar to panicle (*panicula* – panicle), tufted, paniculate [4], [6].
Allium paniculatum (Pale garlic)
Bufoia paniculata (Accepted name [7])
Carex paniculata (Grater tussock-sedge)
Festuca paniculata (East Alpine violet fescue)
Gypsophila paniculata (Panicled baby's-breath, Baby's-breath)
Koelreuteria paniculata (Golden rain tree)
Neslia paniculata (Ball mustard)
Phleum paniculatum (British timothy)
Saxifraga paniculata (Alpine saxifrage, White mountain saxifrage)
- **Papilionaceus, a, um** – resembling butterfly wings (*Papilio* – butterfly) [3].
Orchis papilionacea (synonym of *Anacamptis papilionacea* [7]– Pink butterfly orchid)
- **Parnassifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Parnassia* (grass of Parnassus, bog-stars) plants [6].
Caldesia parnassifolia (Parnassus-leaved water-plantain)
- **Paspalodes, -is** – resembling the genus *Paspalum* (*paspalum* – a Greek name for millet grass) plants [6].
Paspalum paspalodes (synonym of *Paspalum distichum* [7]– Knotgrass)
- **Passerinus, a, um** – sparrow-like (*Passer* – sparrow) [6].
Thymelaea passerina (Spurge flax)
- **Pavoninus, a, um** – relating to or resembling a peacock (*Pavo* – peacock) [4], [6].
Anemone pavonina (synonym of *Anemone hortensis* subsp. *Pavonina* [7] – Peacock windflower: because of a yellow spot at the base of the petals that recalls the peacock's eye [6])
- **Pectinatus, a, um** – resembling a comb, scalloped (*pecten* – comb) [4].
Cardamine pectinata (Accepted name [7]; literally: Comb-like bittercress)
Euphrasia pectinata (Large-bract eyebright)
Potamogeton pectinatus (synonym of *Stuckenia pectinata* [7] – Sago pondweed)
Rubus pectinatus (synonym of *Rubus nigricatus* [7]; literally: Comb-like bramble)
- **Peltatus, a, um** – resembling a round shield: referring to the shape of the leaf and position of the stalk in the center of the leaf (*pelta* – small crescent-like shield) [4].
Nymphoides peltata (Fringed water lily, Yellow floating heart)
Ranunculus peltatus (Pond water-crowfoot)
- **Pelviformis, e** – shaped like a shallow cup, basin-shaped (*pelvis* – basin) [4].
Dianthus pelviformis (Accepted name [7]; literally: Basin-shaped carnation)
- **Penicillatus, a, um** – having a tuft of hair, very finely divided; brush-like: due to the presence of thin organs connected like a brush (*penicillum* – brush) [3], [6].
Ranunculus penicillatus (Chalkstream water-crowfoot)
- **Persicifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the peach tree (*Prunus persica*) [6].
Campanula persicifolia (Peach-leaved bellflower)
Viola persicifolia (Fen violet)

- **Personatus, a, um** – masked, mystified, previously considered something else (*persona* – theatre mask) [3], [6].
Carduus personata (Great marsh thistle)

Note: There is a probable mistake in the agreement – the specific epithet should be *personatus* because the generic name *Carduus* is masculine gender

- **Peucedanoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Peucedanum* (hog fennel) [4], [6].
Seseli peucedanoides (Accepted name [7])
- **Phegopteris** – oak-fern: the epithet combines the Greek words φηγός (oak) and πτέρις (fern) [4], [6].
Thelypteris phegopteris (synonym of *Phegopteris connectilis* [7] – Northern beech fern)
- **Phleoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Phleum* (timothy) plants, rush-like [4], [6].
Phleum phleoides (Boehmer’s cat’s-tail, Purple-stem cat’s-tail)
Trifolium phleoides (Accepted name [7]; literally: Timothy-like clover)
- **Phlomoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Phlomis* (Jerusalem sage) [6].
Verbascum phlomoides (Orange mullein)
- **Physalodes, -is** – resembling the genus *Physalis* (bellows) plants, bladder-like [4].
Nicandra physalodes (Apple-of-Peru, Shoo-fly plant)
- **Physodes, -is** – similar to a bladder, inflated (φῦσα – bladder) [4].
Trifolium physodes (Accepted name [7]; literally: Bladder-like clover)
- **Picroides, -is** – oxtongue-like (*Picris* – oxtongue) [6].
Reichardia picroides (Common bright-eyes, French scorzonera)
Urospermum picroides (Prickly goldenfleece)
- **Pilosellifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Pilosella* (a genus of hairy perennial flowering plants), hawkweed-leaved-like [4].
Convolvulus pilosellifolius (Soft bindweed)
- **Piloselloides, -is** – resembling *Pilosella* (a genus of hairy perennial flowering plants), hawkweed-like [4].
Hieracium piloselloides (synonym of *Pilosella piloselloides* [7] – Tall hawkweed)
- **Pilulifer, era, erum** – bearing globules or small balls: reference to the spherical shape of inflorescences, glands, berries, etc. (*pilula* – globule) [6].
Urtica pilulifera (Roman nettle)
- **Pimpinellifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Pimpinella* (anise) plants [4], [6].
Rosa pimpinellifolia (Burnet rose)
- **Pimpinelloides, -is** – resembling the genus *Pimpinella* (anise), especially due to the appearance of the leaves [6].
Oenanthe pimpinelloides (Corky-fruited water-dropwort)
- **Pinifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Pinus* (pine), pine-leaved [6].
Dianthus pinifolius (Pineleaf garden pink)
- **Pisiformis, e** – pea-like (*Pisum* – pea): reference to the shape of the fruits [6].
Vicia pisiformis (Pale-flower vetch)
- **Plantagineus, a, um** – resembling the genus *Plantago* (plantain) plants, ribwort-like, plantain-like [4], [6].
Echium plantagineum (Purple viper’s-bugloss, Paterson’s curse)
- **Platanifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *Platanus* (plane tree) [6].
Ranunculus platanifolius (Large white buttercup)
- **Platanoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Platanus* (plane tree), plane-tree-like [4].
Acer platanoides (Norway maple)
- **Polyanthemoides, -is** – similar to the *polyanthemum* (with many flowers) species [6].
Ranunculus x polyanthemoides (Accepted hybrid [7]; literally: similar to Multi-flowered buttercup – *Ranunculus polyanthemus*)
- **Polygonifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Polygonum* (knotweed – with many joints, or swollen stem nodes) [6].
Potamogeton polygonifolius (Bog pondweed)
- **Porrifolius, a, um** – having leek-like leaves (*Allium porrum* – leek) [4], [6].
Tragopogon porrifolius (Common salsify, Purple salsify)
- **Portulacoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Portulaca* (purslane) plants [6].
Halimione portulacoides (Sea purslane)
- **Primuliflorus, a, um** – having flowers like the genus *Primula* (primrose) plants [6].
Alkanna primuliflora (Accepted name [7])

- **Pseudoaristatus, a, um** – false-awned (*arista* – awn) [3].
Galium pseudoaristatum (Accepted name [7]; literally: False-awned bedstraw)
- **Pseudoatticus, a, um** – false-Attic (Attica – the classical name for the area of Greece surrounding the city of Athens).
Erysimum pseudoatticum (Accepted name [7]; literally: False-Attic wallflower)
- **Pseudoaxillaris, e** – false-axillary (axillary – located in the leaf axils).
Centaurea pseudoaxillaris (Accepted name [7]; Bulgarian endemic [5])
- **Pseudoconcinus, a, um** – an epithet for another close species: similar and confused with this species (*concinus* – well-made) [6].
Poa pseudoconcinna (synonym of *Poa bulbosa* [7] – Bulbous bluegrass, Bulbous meadow-grass)
- **Pseudodalmaticus, a, um** – false-Dalmatic (Dalmatia – a region on the Adriatic coast of the Balkan Peninsula).
Festuca pseudodalmatica (Accepted name [7]; literally: False-Dalmatic fescue)
- **Pseudofontanus, a, um** – false-spring (growing in running water, of a spring; *fontanus* – spring, fontal).
Taraxacum pseudofontanum (Accepted name [7]; literally: False-spring dandelion)
- **Pseudomontanus, a, um** – false-mountainous (*montanus* – mountain, upland).
Ranunculus pseudomontanus (Accepted name [7]; literally: False-mountainous buttercup)
- **Pseudopectinatus, a, um** – false-comb-like (*pectinatus* – like a comb).
Achillea pseudopectinata (Accepted name [7]; literally: False-comb-like yarrow)
- **Pseudophragmites, -is** – confused with *Phragmites* (*φραγμίτες* – growing on fences or suitable for a fence: name used by Dioscorides for a species whose stems were used for making hedges [6])
Calamagrostis pseudophragmites (Accepted name [7])
- **Pseudosalicifolius, a, um** – false-willow-leaved (*Salix* – willow).
Spiraea x pseudosalicifolia (Artificial hybrid [7]; Confused bridewort)
- **Pseudovernelensis, e** – false-vernelensis (of the locality of Vernelathal in the Silvretta Group in Switzerland, where the holotype was collected [6]).
Taraxacum pseudovernelense (synonym of *Taraxacum paludosiforme* [7]; Bulgarian endemic [5])
- **Pseudovinus, a, um** – false-ovine (*ovinus* – ovine, sheep's) [6].
Festuca pseudovina (synonym of *Festuca pulchra* [7])
- **Pterodes, -is** – wing-like (*πτερόν* – wing).
Tragopogon pterodes (Accepted name [7]; literally: Wing-like goats-beard)
- **Pulegioides, -is** – resembling the plant *pulegium* (flea-dispeller – a type of mint) [4], [6].
Thymus pulegioides (Broad-leaved thyme)
- **Quercinus, a, um** – relating to the genus *Quercus* (oak), oak-like [4], [6].
Lactuca quercina (Accepted name [7]; literally: Oak-leaved lettuce)
- **Ranunculoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Ranunculus* (buttercup) plants [6].
Anemone ranunculoides (Yellow wood anemone, Buttercup anemone)
Bupleurum ranunculoides (Crowfoot-leaved hare's ear)
- **Rapunculoides, -is** – similar to little turnip (rapunculus – little turnip, now an obsolete genus) due to the swollen roots or similar to the cognate species *Campanula rapunculus* [6].
Campanula rapunculoides (Creeping bellflower)
- **Reniformis, e** – kidney-shaped (*ren* – kidney) [4], [6].
Alchemilla reniformis (Accepted name [7]; literally: Reniform lady's mantle)
- **Resedifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Reseda* (mignonette) [6].
Cardamine resedifolia (Mignonette-leaved bittercress)
- **Rhamnoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Rhamnus* (buckthorn) plants [6].
Hippophae rhamnoides (Sea-buckthorn)
- **Rorippifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Rorippa* (yellowcress) plants.
Verbascum roripifolium (Accepted name [7]; literally: Yellowcress-leaved mullein)
- **Rosmarinifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Rosmarinus* (rosemary) plants [6].
Salix rosmarinifolia (Rosemary-leaved willow)
- **Rubioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Rubia* (madder) plants [6].
Galium rubioides (European bedstraw)
Linaria rubioides (Accepted name [7]; literally: Madder-like toadflax)
- **Rutifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Ruta* (rue) plants [6].
Centaurea rutifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Rue-leaved knapweed)
- **Saccifer, era, erum (sacciferus, a, um)** – bag-bearing, pouch-bearing (*saccus* – bag, sac): because of the presence of a spur, labellum, or another sack-shaped organ [6].
Dactylorhiza saccifera (Sack-carrying dactylorhiza)

- **Saginoïdes, -is** – resembling the genus *Sagina* (pearlwort) plants [6].
Sagina saginoïdes (Arctic pearlwort, Alpine pearlwort)
- **Sagittalis, e** – arrow-like; having arrow-shaped, sagittate, pointed organs (*sagitta* – arrow) [4], [6].
Chamaespartium sagittale (synonym of *Genista sagittalis* [7]– Winged broom)
- **Sagittatus, a, um** – arrow-shaped (*sagitta* – arrow) [4], [6].
Arabis sagittata (Accepted name [7]; literally: Arrow-shaped rockcress)
- **Sagittifolius, a, um** – having arrow-shaped leaves (*sagitta* – arrow) [6].
Sagittaria sagittifolia (Arrowhead)
- **Salicarius, a, um** – willow-like, resembling *Salix* (*Salix* – willow) [4].
Lythrum salicaria (Purple loosestrife)

Note: There is a probable mistake in the agreement – the specific epithet should be *salicarium* because the generic name *Lythrum* is neuter gender.

- **Salicifolius, a, um** – having leaves like those of the genus *Salix* (willow), willow-leaved [6].
Ajuga salicifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Willow-leaved bugleweed)
Euphorbia salicifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Willow-leaved spurge)
Helianthemum salicifolium (Willow-leaved rockrose)
Persicaria salicifolia (synonym of *Persicaria decipiens* [7] – Slender knotweed)
Spiraea salicifolia (Willowleaf meadowsweet, Bridewort)
- **Salicinus, a, um** – willow-like, similar to a willow; usually a reference to the leaves (*Salix* – willow) [4], [6].
Inula salicina (Irish fleabane, Willowleaf yellowhead)
- **Salignus, a, um** – willow-like, referring mainly to the leaves (*Salix* – willow) [4], [6].
Aster salignus (synonym of *Synphyotrichum x salignum* [7] – Common Michaelmas-daisy)
Lactuca saligna (Willowleaf lettuce, Least lettuce)
- **Salviifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Salvia* (sage) plants [6].
Cistus salviifolius (Sage-leaved rock-rose)
- **Sambucinus, a, um** – elder-like, resembling the genus *Sambucus* (elder) [4], [6].
Dactylorhiza sambucina (Elder-flowered orchid)
- **Schoenoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Schoenus* (bog-rush), rush-like [4].
Crypsis schoenoides (Swamp pricklegrass, Swamp timothy)
- **Schoenoprasus, a, um** – literally: leek with leaves similar to those of a rush, rush-like leek (a reference to the leaves) [4], [6].
Allium schoenoprasum (Chives)
- **Scleropoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Scleropoa* (hard-pasturage) [3].
Amaranthus scleropoides (Bonebract amaranth)
- **Scoparius, a, um** – similar to a broom or suitable for making brooms (*scopa* – broom) [4], [6].
Artemisia scoparia (Virgate wormwood, Redstem wormwood)
Bromus scoparius (Broom brome, Twiggy brome)
Kochia scoparia (synonym of *Bassia scoparia* [7] – Summer cypress)
- **Scorodoprasus, a, um** – garlic-like leek (the name is used by Dioscorides for a plant with intermediate features: *σκόροδον* – garlic, and *πράσον* – leek [4]).
Allium scorodoprasum (Sand leek, Rocambole)
- **Scorpioides, -is** – scorpion-like, coiled like a tail of a scorpion (referring to the shape of some organs: *scorpio* – scorpion) [4], [6].
Coronilla scorpioides (Annual scorpion-vetch, Yellow crow-vetch)
Myosotis scorpioides (True forget-me-not, Water forget-me-not)
- **Scutatus, a, um** – with a shield, shield-like (a reference to the leaves shape; *scutum* – round shield).
Rumex scutatus (French sorrel, Buckler-leaved sorrel)
- **Scutellatus, a, um** – resembling a small shield, platter-like (*scutelum* – small shield) [4], [6].
Campanula scutellata (Accepted name [7]; literally: Shield-like bellflower)
Veronica scutellata (Marsh speedwell, Skullcap speedwell, Grass-leaf speedwell)
- **Secalinus, a, um** – resembling the genus *Secale* (rye), rye-like [4], [6].
Bromus secalinus (Rye brome)
Hordeum secalinum (Meadow barley, False rye barley)
- **Selaginoides, -is** – resembling the genus *Selago* (moss-like plant), clubmoss-like [4], [6].
Selaginella selaginoides (Lesser clubmoss, Club spikemoss, Northern spikemoss)
- **Serpyllifolius, a, um** – having leaves like those of *Thymus serpyllum* (Wild thyme) [4], [6].

Arenaria serpyllifolia (Thyme-leaf sandwort)

Veronica serpyllifolia (Thyme-leaved speedwell)

- **Sesameus, a, um** – resembling the genus *Sesamum* (sesame) plants [6].
Astragalus sesameus (Purple milk-vetch)
- **Silaifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *Silaum* (an old generic name of an umbelliferous plant cited by Pliny) [6].
Cnidium silaifolium (Accepted name [7])
Oenanthe silaifolia (Narrow-leaved water-dropwort)
- **Simulans, -antis** – similar, resembling, or imitating another species [4], [6].
Dianthus simulans (Cushion alpine pink; Balkan endemic)
- **Spat(h)ulatus, a, um** – spatulate: with leaves, bracts, scales, petals, or other spatula-shaped organs (*spat(h)ula* – small spathe) [6].
Campanula spatulata (Accepted name [7]; literally: Spatulate bellflower)
Linum spathulatum (synonym of *Linum hirsutum* subsp. *spathulatum* [7]; literally: Spatulate flax)
- **Spathulisepalus, a, um** – having spatulate sepals (*spathula* – small spathe).
Verbascum spathulisepalum (Accepted name [7]; Balkan endemic)
- **Speltoides, -is** – similar to *spelta* (*spelta* – a type of wheat, formerly widely cultivated in Southern Europe) [3], [6].
Aegilops speltoides (Goatgrass)
- **Spiraeifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Spiraea* (spirea) plants [6].
Inula spiraeifolia (synonym of *Pentanema spiraeifolium* [7])
- **Stellaris, e** – star-like, with spreading rays (a reference usually to the shape of the flowers; *stella* – star) [4], [6].
Saxifraga stellaris (synonym of *Micranthes stellaris* [7] – Starry saxifrage, Hairy kidney-wort)
- **Stellatus, a, um** – star-shaped, having spreading, star-like rays (*stella* – star) [4], [6].
Rhagadiolus stellatus (Endive daisy)
- **Striatiformis, e** – striped, groove-like, ridged (*stria* – groove), for the streaked appearance [4], [6].
Chenopodium striatiforme (synonym of *Chenopodium strictum* [5] – Striped goosefoot)
- **Subulatus, a, um** – awl-shaped, needle-like (*subula* – awl) [4].
Phleum subulatum (Italian timothy)
Plantago subulata (Awl-leaved plantain)
Sedum subulatum (synonym of *Petrosedum subulatum* [7]; literally: Awl-shaped stonecrop)
- **Tanacetifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *Tanacetum* (tansy), in particular of *T. vulgare*, or finely divided with toothed segments [6].
Phacelia tanacetifolia (Lacy phacelia, Purple tansy)
- **Telephioides, -is** – resembling the plant *telephium* (the name originates from a Greek name of a plant considered a symbol of reciprocated love [4]).
Andrachne telephioides (Bastard orpine)
- **Thalictroides, -is** – resembling the genus *Thalictrum* (meadow-rue) plants [6].
Isopyrum thalictroides (Rue-leaved isopyrum)
- **Thapsoides, -is** – similar to *Verbascum thapsus* (Great mullein). The specific epithet *thapsus* was first used by Theophrastus for a plant from the Island of Thapsus [4].
Inula thapsoides (Accepted name [7])
- **Thelypteroides, -is** – resembling the genus *Thelypteris* (maiden fern) plants [6].
Thelypteris thelypteroides (synonym of *Thelypteris palustris* [5] – Marsh fern)
- **Thesioides, -is** – resembling the genus *Thesium* (a type of bulbous plant in Pliny) [4].
Haplophyllum thesioides (Accepted name [7])
- **Thymifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *Thymus* (thyme), thyme-leaved [6].
Lythrum thymifolia (Thymeleaf loosestrife)

Note: There is a probable mistake in the agreement – the specific epithet should be *thymifolium* because the generic name *Lythrum* is neuter gender.

Silene thymifolia (Accepted name [7]; literally: Thyme-leaved catchfly)

- **Thyrsoides, -is** – similar to a rod, baton (*thyrsus* – an ornamental wand tipped with a pine cone): a reference to the inflorescences' pyramidal disposition [6].
Campanula thyrsoides (Accepted name [7])
- **Trichoides, -is** – resembling hair (*θρίξ* – hair), hair-like: for the filiform leaves [6].
Potamogeton trichoides (Hairlike pondweed)
- **Triniifolius, a, um** – having leaves like *Trinia* (a genus of umbelliferous plants) [6].

- Scabiosa triniifolia* (Accepted name [7]; Balcan endemic [5])
- **Turritus, a, um** – tower-shaped (*turris* – tower): for the upright vertical posture [6].
Arabis turrita (synonym of *Pseudoturritis turrita* [7])
 - **Ulmarius, a, um** – elm-like, resembling the genus *Ulmus* (*Ulmus* – elm) [6].
Filipendula ulmaria (Meadowsweet)
 - **Umbellatus, a, um** – umbellate, with umbrella-shaped inflorescences (all branches arising from the same point (*umbella* – parasol) [4].
Alyssum umbellatum (Umbellate madwort)
Butomus umbellatus (Flowering rush)
Hieracium umbellatum (Narrow-leaved hawkweed)
Holosteum umbellatum (Jagged chickweed)
Hypericum umbellatum (Accepted name [7]; literally: Umbellate St. John's wort)
Ornithogalum umbellatum (Garden star-of-Bethlehem)
Rindera umbellata (Accepted name [7])
Sorbus umbellata (synonym of *Aria umbellata* [7])
 - **Urticifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Urtica* (nettle) plants, i. e., ovate, with a serrated margin, rounded, with acute apex [6].
Veronica urticifolia (Nettle-leaved speedwell)
 - **Viciifolius, a, um** – having leaves like the genus *Vicia* (vetch) plants [6].
Onobrychis viciifolia (Common sainfoin)
 - **Virgatus, a, um** – similar to a rod, having straight slender twigs (*virga* – rod, wand) [4], [6].
Lythrum virgatum (European wand loosestrife)
Salvia virgata (Wand sage, Southern meadow sage)
 - **Vomeraceus, a, um** – similar to plowshare (*vomer* – plowshare), due to the shape of the labellum that recalls it [6].
Serapias vomeracea (Long-lipped serapias, Plow-share serapias)
 - **Zygioides, -is** – resembling *zygis* (a type of thyme cited by Dioscorides [6]); yoke-like (paired flowers) [4].
Thymus zygioides (Accepted name [7])

3. Types of adjectives

3.1. Derivative adjectives formed through different suffixes:

Much of the suffixes used are polysemantic, so in several epithets additional connotations related to the appearance, shape, or presence of an organ or part of an organ in the particular botanical species are possible, but in the current research, the meaning indicating similarity, connectivity, or likeness is assumed as leading.

- *-ace-* – denominative adjectives, meaning “made of, similar to, resembling”: *alliaceus* (resembling onion), *hederaceus* (pertaining to ivy), *margaritaceus* (pearl-like).
- *-al-* / *-ar-* – denominative adjectives, meaning “pertaining to, similar to”: *ligularis* (strap-like), *sagittalis* (arrow-like).
- *-ari-* – adjectives meaning “pertaining to”: *cicutarius* (resembling water hemlock), *hirundinarius* (like a swallow), *scoparius* (similar to a broom).
- *-at-* – denominative adjectives, meaning “resembling, equipped with, possession”: *clavatus* (club-shaped), *lanceolatus* (lance-shaped), *stellatus* (star-like), *virgatus* (similar to a rod). Much of these epithets can also be interpreted as describing the external appearance and shape of the plant: *capitatus* (resembling a head, having head-shaped inflorescences), *scutatus* (like a shield or having shield-shaped parts).
- *-eus* – denominative adjectives, meaning “similarity by analogy, close resemblance”: *conopseus* (gnat-like), *gramineus* (grass-like), *sesameus* (resembling sesame).
- *-in-* – denominative adjectives, meaning “relating to, likeness, possession”: *leporinus* (resembling or pleasing to hares), *quercinus* (relating to oak), *secalinus* (resembling the rye).

Note: This suffix could also indicate the place of growth: *abietinus* (like fir or growing in fir forests).

- *-ius* – denominative adjectives, meaning “relation, belonging”: *ciconius* (relating to stork), *scordius* (garlicky).

There also are single examples for derivative adjectives formed through other suffixes: *anisiacus* (relating to anise), *verbenacus* (resembling vervain), *turritus* (tower-like), *myrsinites* (resembling myrtle), *salignus* (willow-like), *laureolus* (similar to small laurel).

Several derivative adjectives contain two suffixes to highlight an additional nuance in the indicated attribute: *clypeatus* (shield-like) and *clypeolatus* (shaped like a small shield), *hamosus* (hook-like) and *hamulosus* (similar to a small hook).

3.2. Compound adjectives

The most numerous are the adjectives formed through the word-formative component *-oides* (*-oideus*). The word-formative component *-oides* originates from the Greek noun *εἶδος* (view, image, appearance) meaning “similarity, resemblance” – usually with another plant species: *absinthioides* (similar to absinthe), *amygdaloides* (almond-like), *fabarioides* (resembling a bean), *ranunculoides* (resembling a buttercup), *thesioides* (resembling the genus Thesium). More rarely, this morpheme indicates proximity with an object: *botryoides* (like a cluster of grapes), *deltoides* (shaped like the Greek letter delta), *trichoides* (similar to hair). For each adjective, the basic noun from which it is formed is indicated.

Secondly, by frequency of use, are the adjectives with a second word-formative component *-folius* / *-florus* or their Greek doublets *-phyllus* / *-anthus* (*folium, i n* – leaf; *flos, floris m* – flower, blossom). They indicate similarity to the shape of the leaves or the flowers of another plant species (*abrotanifolius*, *betonicifolius*, *erucifolius*, *narcissiflorus*, *opulifolius*, *primuliflorus*, etc.), added in brackets.

The next group of adjectives includes these ones formed through the word-formative component *-formis* (*forma, aef* – form, shape). Most of these compound adjectives indicate similarity to another botanical genus ((*amygdaliformis* – almond-like; *festuciformis* – fescue-shaped, *pisiformis* – pea-like, etc.). In a few cases, however, there is a similarity to the form of a particular object (*disciformis* – disc-shaped, *pelviformis* – basin-shaped, etc.). These epithets in a more general sense mean “general appearance, shape”, but in the present study leading is the idea for emphasis on proximity and similarity to a particular object. For the same reason, the epithet *striatiformis* (striped), which could be interpreted as a definition of coloring, is also included.

There is a small group of compound adjectives formed through the verb stem *-fer* (*fero* carry) that signify the presence of an organ or resemblance to an object: *apifer* (bearing bees), *insectifer* (bearing insects), *pilulifer* (bearing globules), etc.

In particular, must be noted the adjectives formed through the Greek stem *pseudo-* (*ψεύδω* lie, mislead). They indicate an imaginary similarity in appearance (*pseudoaristatus* false-awned; *pseudosalicifolius* false-willow-leaved) or place of spreading (*pseudoatticus* false-Attic; *pseudodalmaticus* false-dalmatic; *pseudofontanus* false-spring; *pseudomontanus* false-mountain), with another species having, in reality, such a quality. This word-formative component is commonly used to distinguish a genus or species from that with which it was previously confused or to avoid the formation of a homonym.

3.3. Participles

It is interesting to note that two participles are figuratively used: *graecizans* (that imitates or reminds any Greek plants) and *personatus* (masked, mystified, previously considered something else).

4. Conclusion

Specific botanical epithets carry a variety of information relating to the morphological characteristics of the species, place of spread, particular features, similarities, or differences with other earlier studied and described species.

Besides the particular information, however, Latin names reflect in chronological perspective the development of ideas and knowledge for each species. Particularly indicative in this regard are epithets denoting the likeness and similarity to another plant species or object. In the process of researching and describing new plant species, scientists often use comparison with already known taxonomic units to achieve a more complete and precise description and to avoid possible confusion when considering closely related and difficult-to-distinguish species. A good knowledge of the terminological Latin language and the various word-formation methods is essential to achieve this goal.

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